

MANUFACTURING OF CARBON- AND GLASS-FIBER COMPOSITES USING FRONTAL POLYMERIZATION

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ABSTRACT

We fabricate unidirectional carbon fiber-reinforced dicyclopentadiene (DCPD) composites cured by the frontal polymerization technique. A homogenized thermo-chemical model is proposed to study the manufacturing process. We then solve the proposed model using a nonlinear finite element solver to investigate the evolution of the temperature and degree of cure during the fabrication process. Simulation of curing process of glass fiber-reinforced DCPD composites and carbon fiber-reinforced epoxy composites are added to demonstrate the efficiency of the proposed framework and to study the effects of different fibers on the front characteristics; maximum temperature and front velocity.

1 INTRODUCTION

Fiber-Reinforced Polymer Composites (FRPCs) are vital to today's aerospace, automotive, marine, construction, and energy industries and will be integral to the next generation of lightweight, energy-efficient structures in these applications owing to their excellent specific stiffness and strength, thermal stability and chemical resistance [1]. Yet, the fabrication process of FRPCs is very challenging and has long been a detriment to their wider use. The manufacturing of high-performance thermoset composites mainly relies on the bulk polymerization of the monomer at high temperatures (around 180 °C) for several hours under a combined external pressure and internal vacuum, resulting in a long and energy-intensive process. Curing is generally accomplished using large autoclaves, and the manufacturing cost has been shown to increase exponentially with the composite panel size [2]. In a recent publication [1], we proposed Frontal Polymerization (FP) as an alternative to prevalent curing techniques of fiber-reinforced thermoset polymer composites, in an effort to address the aforementioned manufacturing challenges and achieve substantial savings in both time and energy during the fabrication process. FP is defined as a process in which a localized reaction zone propagates through the monomer by converting into polymer [3,4], resulting in a self-sustained process where the heat consumed by the advancing front balances the heat generated by the exothermic reaction. FP has been shown to be significantly faster than oven- or autoclave-curing processes, and it can be accelerated further by adding conductive elements [5].

The present study focuses on the modeling of key differences in the FP-based manufacturing of carbon- and glass-fiber composites. These two types of reinforcing fibers have very distinct thermal

properties, which are expected to strongly affect the thermo-chemical reaction-diffusion processes associated with the propagation of the polymerization front through the composite.

2 EXPERIMENTS

Experimental investigation of the composite manufacturing process is done through fabrication of fiber reinforced polymer composite (FRPC) laminates wherein the thickness and ply count are controlled to tailor the fiber volume fraction of the composite. The manufacture of these laminates is facilitated via an open molding technique for repeatable and simple experimental setup. The mold is manufactured using an insulating polyisocyanurate foam sheet (Fibre Glast Part Number 448-D), rigid green fiber glass substrates (sourced from lab), quick disconnect thermocouples (Omega Part Number SCPSS-020U-36), and abrasion-resistant polyurethane rubber that does not react with the poly(DCPD) (McMaster-Carr Part Number 8716K62). For each composite panel the following consumables are used for manufacturing each laminate; Stretchlon® 800 bagging film (Fibre Glast Part Number 1688), Unidirectional weave of Toray T700 12 K carbon fiber (300 gm-2, Composite Envisions, F-869), Dicyclopentadiene (DCPD), 5-ethylidene-2-norbornene (ENB), second-generation Grubbs' catalyst (GC2), phenylcyclohexane, and Tri Tributyl phosphite (TBP) all of which were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich and used as received. The FP resin was prepared following the procedure outlined by Robertson et al. ([1]). Manufacturing the FRPC is done by creating the mold in sandwich fashion (Fig. 1). The inherently low viscosity of the matrix permits the use of a volumetric syringe to infiltrate the fabric preform within the mold. Data acquisition was started in Labview 2015. The frontal polymerization of DCPD was initiated using a point heat source, via soldering iron.

Figure 1: The schematic of the full mold (a), omitting the bar clamps for simplicity, with a cross sectional view of the internal components of the mold (b) and (c) infiltration of the mold and fabric preform with matrix via volumetric syringe.

Maximum temperature was extracted from the thermocouple data (Fig. 2). The maximum temperature was taken from the peak value of the thermocouple data.

Figure 2: Thermocouple data output for $\phi = 0\%$. The sharp onset is a result of the sampling rate (100 Hz) and the sharp front passing through the region of interest.

The fiber volume fraction of the composites was determined using the following equation:

$$\phi = f_A \cdot n / \rho_f \cdot t \quad (1)$$

In which ϕ is the fiber volume fraction, f_A is the areal density of the fabric, n is the number of plies, ρ_f is the density of the fabric, and t is the thickness of the final laminate. These experiments yielded samples with the tailorable and controlled volume fractions allowing for the extraction of the temperature (Fig. 3).

Figure 3: Thermocouple data output for $\phi = 0\%$. The sharp onset is a result of the sampling rate (100 Hz) and the sharp front passing through the region of interest.

The experimental results show a monotonic decrease in maximum temperature with increasing volume fraction of carbon fiber, caused by the heat transfer through the carbon fibers.

3 NUMERICAL MODELING

We propose a homogenized model to study the FP-based manufacturing of uni-directional carbon- and glass-fiber-reinforced composites as

$$\begin{cases} \bar{\kappa} \frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial x^2} + (1 - \phi) \bar{\rho} H_r \frac{\partial \alpha}{\partial t} = \bar{\rho} \bar{C}_p \frac{\partial T}{\partial t}, \\ \frac{\partial \alpha}{\partial t} = f(T)g(\alpha), \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

where T denotes the temperature, α the degree of cure, κ the thermal conductivity coefficient, ϕ the volume fraction of fiber phase, H_r the total enthalpy of the reaction, ρ the density, C_p the specific heat, t the time, $f(T)$ the Arrhenius's equation, and $g(\alpha)$ the cure kinetics of the reaction. The overbars denote the homogenized properties of the composite. We then solve the model using a nonlinear finite element solver in which we combine the Preconditioned Jacobian-Free Newton Krylov scheme and an implicit Euler time integration method to solve the nonlinear reaction-diffusion model at each time step. The numerical analysis involves a robust mesh adaptivity module, which is essential to capture the high gradients of the temperature and the degree of cure around the moving polymerization front.

3-1 CARBON- AND GLASS FIBER-REINFORCED DCPD COMPOSITES

For this study, we consider the reinforcing phase to be unidirectional carbon- and E-glass-fibers. The material properties were obtained from Azom.com [6] and are presented in Table 1. The chemistry used for this study is a mixture of 5-ethylidene norbornene ENB (5%), 2nd generation Grubbs' catalyst (0.064%), Toluene (2-5%), Tributyl phosphate (0.02%) as the inhibitor. The cure kinetic parameters of DCPD are listed in Table 2. We have used the PT model for the cure kinetics of DCPD [1].

	$\kappa \left(\frac{W}{mK}\right)$	$\rho \left(\frac{kg}{m^3}\right)$	$C_p \left(\frac{J}{kgK}\right)$
DCPD	0.152	980	1600
Carbon-fiber	9.5	2560	800
E-glass-fiber	1.275	2575	802.5

Table 1: Material properties for generic carbon and E-glass fibers.

Parameter	Value
A (1/s)	8.85e15
E (kJ/mol)	110.75
n	1.72
m	0.77
C	14.48
α_c	0.41

Table 2: Cure kinetics parameters of DCPD.

Fig. 4 shows the cure and temperature profiles for 3 values of glass-fiber volume fraction 0% (neat DCPD), 25% and 50%. From the solution profiles we can see that as the fiber volume fraction increases, the front becomes elongated and the maximum temperature associated with the front decreases.

Figure 4: Temperature and solution profiles for fiber volume fractions 0%, 25% and 50%.

Fig. 5 provides a summary of the 1-D transient simulations for E-glass/DCPD composites. We observe that the velocity of the front initially decreases slowly until a fiber volume fraction of 15% and decreases significantly thereafter with subsequent increase in fiber concentration. However, the temperature of the front reduces monotonically with increase in fiber volume fraction.

Figure 5: Summary of transient simulations for E-glass-fiber/DCPD composites.

Considering the material properties shown in Table 1, we see that the thermal conductivity of the E-glass-fibers is an order of magnitude greater than that of DCPD. Therefore, as fiber volume fraction increases, so does the effective thermal conductivity of the composite. As a result, some part of the heat released during polymerization is diffused further along the domain and preheats the monomer and by doing so, aids the FP process. Alternatively, this effect can also be understood by considering the increasing difference between the results of the simulations and the analytical prediction for the maximum temperature, and from the elongation of the temperature solution profile showed in Fig. 4.

The amount of monomer available in the system keeps reducing as fiber volume fraction increases. This leads to a decrease in the total heat released during polymerization, which impedes the

propagation of the reaction front, leading to a drastic decrease in the front velocity and temperature. 60% is the critical value of fiber volume fraction, beyond which there is an acute shortage of resin to maintain FP.

Fig. 6 depicts a comparison between carbon-fiber/DCPD and glass-fiber/DCPD composites. As volume fraction of glass fiber increases, the front velocity monotonically decreases. However, it is not the case for the carbon fiber composites where two distinct modes of behavior are seen. First, front velocity increases and then it starts to decrease due to the lack of monomer in the system which is the only source of heat during the curing process.

Figure 6: Comparison between E-glass-fiber/DCPD and carbon-fiber/DCPD composites.

3-2 CARBON FIBER-REINFORCED EPOXY COMPOSITES

Due to its excellent mechanical properties, resistance to thermal stress and chemical degradation, epoxy has been widely used for composites in many applications, especially in the aerospace industry. Frontal polymerization in epoxy system has been previously reported [3,7], which provides great potential for energy-efficient epoxy matrix composites manufacturing. To investigate the use of FP for manufacturing epoxy-matrix unidirectional fiber composites, we adopted the epoxy system reported by Frulloni and co-workers [3]. This epoxy system contains 7.2 parts in weight of diglycidyl ether of bisphenol A (DGEBA; M_n of 377) and 1.0 part in weight of diethylenetriamine (DETA). The physical parameters of this epoxy system are listed in Table 1.

Parameter	Value
ρ (kg/m ³)	1190
κ (W/(mK))	0.19
C_p (J/(kgK))	2230

Table 3: Physical properties of the epoxy system.

The cure kinetics of the above-mentioned epoxy system is characterized by

$$\frac{\partial \alpha}{\partial t} = (k_1 + k_2 \alpha^m)(\alpha_{max} - \alpha)^n \quad (3)$$

where

$$k_1 = A_1 \exp\left(-\frac{E_1}{RT}\right),$$

$$k_2 = A_2 \exp\left(-\frac{E_2}{RT}\right),$$

and

$$\alpha_{max} = pT + q.$$

Cure kinetics of the epoxy is listed in Table 2, and the heat of reaction H_r is 550 kJ/g.

Parameter	Value
A_1 (1/s)	9.8764e6
A_2 (1/s)	2.2266e2
E_1 (kJ/mol)	6.4735e4
E_2 (kJ/mol)	3.1561e4
M	1
N	1.07
p (1/°C)	6.96e-3
Q	4.57e-1

Table 4: Cure kinetics parameters of the epoxy system.

Using the homogenized model, we conduct frontal polymerization in the epoxy system at different fiber volume fraction as shown in Fig. 7. It is observed that the maximum front velocity occurs at about 30% fiber volume fraction, and is about 3 times large as the front velocity in neat resin. The highest fiber volume fraction it can reach is 65%, which indicates its great potential in applications where high fiber volume fraction is desired. The front velocity in the composite case are all higher than the front velocity in neat resin, which is another attractive feature that provides higher manufacturing efficiency.

Figure 7: Front velocity as a function of fiber volume fraction for epoxy composites.

The maximum temperature from the simulation is compared with the analytical solution in Fig. 8. The maximum temperature is higher than the maximum temperature in the DCPD matrix case, mainly because of the high heat of reaction of the epoxy system. The maximum temperature still shows expected decreasing trend as fiber volume fraction increases, and reasonable match is observed between the simulation results and the analytical solution.

Figure 8: Maximum temperature as a function of fiber volume fraction compared with analytical solution for epoxy composites.

4 CONCLUSIONS

A homogenized thermo-chemical model is proposed to study the curing process of fiber-reinforced polymer composites using frontal polymerization. We then solve the model via a nonlinear finite element solver and obtain front characteristic including maximum temperature and front velocity. As anticipated, the high thermal conductivity of the carbon fibers leads to a higher front velocity at lower values of the fiber volume fraction. However, as ϕ increases, the decrease in available energy of reaction in the matrix leads to a progressive reduction in the front speed. In the case of glass fibers, however, we observe a steady decrease in the predicted front speed, owing to the small value of the thermal conductivity of glass fibers. The dependence of the maximum temperature of ϕ is relatively similar, except for larger values of ϕ for which the increasing contribution of diffusion in the carbon fiber case leads to a slightly lower maximum temperature behind the polymerization front.

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